

Shared anchors for floating wind turbines

Test SW_01

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1 Introduction

This data report contains the experimental results of experiment SW_01 performed on 04 September 2023. The centrifuge test consisted on two lateral load tests and a pullout test on suction anchors installed in normally consolidated clay.

2 General Information

The centrifuge test consisted on two lateral load tests and a pullout test on small scale suction anchors. The anchors were installed in reconstituted Speswhite kaolin applying consolidation pressures aiming at reproducing a normally consolidated clay profile.

This experiment was performed in the framework of ShareWind project: shared anchors for floating wind turbines (Grant agreement 101106921-<https://doi.org/10.3030/101106921>).

3 Model preparation

For the centrifuge experiment, a circular container with a diameter of 895 mm and a height of 700 mm was employed. The soft clay ground was built by consolidating 4 layers of kaolin subjected to different pre-consolidation pressures. Speswhite kaolin was mixed with water aiming at reaching an initial water content of the mixture of around 80% for all the layers. Table 1 shows the target consolidation pressures for each layer aiming at simulating a normally

consolidated clay profile. For the vertical effective stress, it was employed a total unit weight for the clay $\gamma = 16.5 \text{ kN/m}^3$ and an effective unit weight $\gamma' = 6.5 \text{ kN/m}^3$. For the calculation of the target vertical effective stresses it was assumed a scale factor between the prototype and the model $N=75$.

Table 1: Proposed load sequence for the oedometer tests

	Model			Prototype			
	From (mm)	To (mm)	Thickness (mm)	From (m)	To (m)	Average Depth (m)	Average vertical eff. stress (kPa)
Layer 4	0	80	80	0.0	6.0	3.0	19.5
Layer 3	80	165	85	6.0	12.4	9.2	59.7
Layer 2	165	255	90	12.4	19.1	15.8	102.4
Layer 1	255	350	95	19.1	26.3	22.7	147.5

Figure 1: Vertical effective stress profile for the clay

Before installing the first layer of clay, a layer of sand with a thickness of 110 mm was placed at the base of the model. This to allow the drainage of water from the clay. The consolidation pressures were applied by using a hydraulic piston with a digital control system to regulate the pressures. The initial pressure applied to the clay corresponded to the one provided by the self weight of the piston, equivalent to 6.9 kPa. Figure 2 shows a view of the loading system and the installation of one of the clay layers in the model container.

Table 2 summarizes the initial and final thickness of the reconstituted clay layers subjected to the target range of pressures. The initial pressure applied to all the clay layers corresponds to the exerted by the own weight of the hydraulic press (6.9 kPa).

Figure 2: Setup for the consolidation of the clay

Table 2: Consolidation of clay layers and loading sequence

	H ₀ - Initial height(mm)	H _f - Final height (mm)	H _f /H ₀	Load Sequence (kPa)
Clay 4 (Top)	120.0	101.0	0.84	6.9 - 19.5
Clay 3	105.0	75.0	0.71	6.9 - 14 - 28 -60
Clay 2	110.0	80.0	0.73	6.9 - 15 - 28 - 60 - 102
Clay 1 (bottom)	110.0	79.0	0.72	6.9 - 14 -28-60 -147
Total	445.0	335.0		

4 Experimental setup

The experimental setup consisted on the installation of three suction piles to carry out two lateral loading tests and one pullout test. The scale factor between the prototype and the model was $N=75$. Table 1 presents the model and prototype dimensions for the centrifuge test. The height of the clay before the centrifuge test was 335 mm, after the re-consolidation in flight of the clay, the total height of the clay bed was 315 mm leading to an additional settlement of around 20 mm.

The centrifuge model was instrumented with pore pressure transducers installed in the clay at four locations: i) at a distance of $1D$ below the base of the suction anchors, ii) at a depth corresponding to the base of the suction anchors, iii) at the top of the anchors and iv) at the surface of the clay to monitor the height of the water table above the model. The pore pressures transducers in the clay were installed during the consolidation of the different layers. In addition, displacement transducers (LVDTs) were installed at the surface of the clay and in contact with the top of the suction anchors. The actuator employed to apply the loads was instrumented with a load cell and a laser transducer. For the characterization tests in terms of undrained shear strength of the clay it was employed a T-bar with a diameter of 5mm and a length of 20 mm, leading to a projected area of 100 mm^2

Table 3: Prototype and model dimensions

Dimension	Model (1/75)	Prototype
<u>Suction Anchor</u>		
Material	Stainless steel	–
D , diameter	60 mm	4.5 m
L , length	200 mm	15.0 m
L/D	3.3	3.3
t , Wall thickness	0.41 mm	3.0 cm
D/t	150	150
W , weight	256.3 g	108.0 t
W' , buoyant weight	218.5 g	92.1 t
<u>Model Container</u>		
Height	700 mm	52.5 m
Height extension	160 mm	12.0 m
Diameter	895 mm	67.1 m
Water table	300 mm	22.5 m
<u>Soil layers</u>		
Clay 4 (Top)	101 mm	7.6 m
Clay 3	75 mm	5.6 m
Clay 2	80 mm	6.0 m
Clay 1 (bottom)	79 mm	5.9 m
Drainage layer	110 mm	8.3 m

The anchors were installed at 1g by pushing them inside the clay. The installation depth corresponded to the totality of the length of the anchors (200 mm). This process was carried out by opening the top valves of the anchors. In the sequence, the pore pressure transducers were installed at the top of the anchors. Then, the top valves are closed, including the one connected to the cables of the PPTs. Figure 3 shows a view of the suction anchors and the installation process in the clay.

Figure 3: Suction anchors installation

After the installation of the suction anchors, a set of gantries and supports were installed to place an unidirectional actuator top apply the loads to the anchors. Figure 4 presents the test setup for the vertical loading test (pullout) and Figure 5 the setup for a lateral loading test. Figure 6 presents details of the centrifuge experiment including a pulley employed for the lateral loading test, a light system and cameras employed to follow the loading tests. Both the cameras and the lights are designed to be submerged under the water table. Table 4 summarizes the testing parameters and the identification of the anchors.

Table 4: Identification of loading tests for the suction anchors

Anchor	Load condition	Loading rate (model scale)
1	Vertical	112 mm/min
2	Lateral	23 mm/min
3	Lateral	114 mm/min

Figure 4: Vertical load test setup

Figure 5: Lateral load test setup - Anchor 2

Figure 6: Lateral load test setup- Anchor 3

Figure 7: Details of the centrifuge test

5 Test chronology

The centrifuge test was carried out in three stages that took place in three consecutive days as follows:

- Day 1 (05-Sep-2023): lateral load test on top of anchor 2.
- Day 2 (06-Sep-2023): lateral pullout on top of anchor 1.
- Day 3 (07-Sep-2023): lateral load test on top of anchor 3.

5.1 Anchor 2 - Lateral load test

This test consisted on applying monotonic load on top of the suction anchor at a loading rate of 23 mm/min:

- 07h00: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 07h00: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 07h55: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 07h55 to 14h30: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 14h30: T-bar test #1 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h35: lateral load test at a load rate of 23 mm/min and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h35: video recording of the lateral test.
- 14h45: T-bar test #2 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 15h00: T-bar test #3 (cyclic) at a load rate of 3 mm/s, 10 cycles and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 15h30: stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 15h30: end of the centrifuge test.

5.2 Anchor 1 - Vertical load test

This test consisted on a pullout test at a loading rate of 112 mm/min:

- 07h30: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 07h30: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 08h00: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 08h00 to 14h15: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 14h15: T-bar test #4 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h20: T-bat test #5 (cyclic) at a load rate of 3 mm/s, 10 cycles and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 14h29: video recording of the lateral test.
- 14h29: pullout test at a load rate of 112 mm/min and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 15h00: stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 15h00: end of the centrifuge test.

5.3 Anchor 3 - Lateral load test

This test consisted on applying monotonic load on top of the suction anchor at a loading rate of 114 mm/min:

- 08h00: Start of the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 08h00: Start of the centrifuge test.
- 08h30: Arrival at the testing level of 75g.
- 08h30 to 15h00: re-consolidation of the clay.
- 15h02: T-bar test #6 at a load rate of 3 mm/s and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 15h07: T-bat test #7 (cyclic) not performed due to a malfunction of the load cell.
- 15h29: video recording of the lateral test.
- 15h30: lateral load test at a rate of 114 mm/min and sampling frequency of 100 Hz.
- 15h35: stop the data acquisition at a frequency of 1 Hz.
- 15h35: end of the centrifuge test.

6 Test Results

6.1 Pullout test - Anchor 1

Figure 7 presents the raw data of the pullout test. The raw data corresponds to the results in terms of model scale employing the instrument calibration factors of the laboratory database. The data acquisition was carried out by using the system Quantum-X by HBK (Link). The data results show the force recorded by the load cell of the actuator with the displacement recorded by a laser sensor to monitor the applied displacements. The pore pressure measurements correspond to three locations: i) at a distance of 1D below the base of the suction anchors, ii) at a depth corresponding to the base of the suction anchors and iii) at the top of the anchors. The pore pressure transducer identified as P174 presented malfunction.

Figure 8: Raw data - Pullout test - Model scale

6.2 Lateral load test - Anchor 2 and Anchor 3

Figure 8 presents the lateral load tests. The data results show the force recorded by the load cell of the actuator with the displacement recorded by a laser sensor to monitor the applied displacements. The pore pressure measurements correspond to three locations: i) at a distance of 1D below the base of the suction anchors, ii) at a depth corresponding to the base of the suction anchors and iii) at the top of the anchors. The pore pressure transducer identified as P170 presented malfunction.

Figure 9: Raw data - Lateral load - Model scale

6.3 Strength characterization tests

Figure 10 displays the strength characterization tests of the clay in terms of the undrained shear strength. The T-bar employed has a diameter of 5 mm and a length of 20 mm, leading to a projected area $A = 100\text{mm}^2$. For the calculation of the undrained shear strength profiles it was employed the recorded data of a potentiometer attached to the T-bar actuator and the force recordings (F) of a load cell placed on top of the T-bar.

Figure 10: Undrained shear strength profiles

For the calculations of the undrained shear strength profiles, it was employed the following relationship:

$$s_u = \frac{q}{N_t} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$q = F/A \quad (2)$$

and $N_t = 10.5$ corresponding to the T-bar factor (Stewart and Randolph, 1991).

7 Data sets

The data sets are presented in terms of model scale. The scaling laws to be applied to the different magnitudes described are presented in literature related with centrifuge testing (i.e., Madabhushi, 2014). The data sets are the raw data obtained from the data logging system, then offsets need to be applied to obtain loads or excess pore pressures starting from zero. The files are stored in two formats, .mat files in case the used has access to Matlab and non-proprietary format .csv files. A script is provided to convert the .MAT files into .csv.

7.1 Load tests

For the project, the data sets for the loading tests are identified following this structure:

SW_x_xx_xxx_xxxx

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
x	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
xx	Anchor identifier: 1, 2, 3.
xxx	Load type: H(horizontal), V (vertical), I (inclined), M (multidirectional)
xxxx	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_01_1_H_MO corresponds to test 01, on anchor 1, subjected to horizontal load (H), monotonic (MO).

7.2 T-bar tests

For the T-bar tests, the data sets are identified as follows:

SW_y_yy_yyy

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
y	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
yy	T-bar consecutive identifier: TBAR1, TBAR2, TBAR3.
yyy	MO (monotonic), CY (cyclic)

For example, data set SW_01 TBAR1 _MO corresponds to centrifuge test 01, T-bar number 1 of type monotonic (MO).

7.3 Data files

The loading tests, horizontal (H) and vertical (V) contain six columns organised as follows:

File **SW_01_1_V_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F110.ACT.FORCE	Force recorded by the actuator in DaN (Deca Newtons)
3	ACT.DISPLLASER.GTX80	Displacement recorded by the load actuator in mm
4	P148	Pore pressures at the top of the anchor in kPa
5	P174	Pore pressures at the bottom of the anchor in kPa
6	P179	Pore pressures at one diameter depth below the anchor in kPa

File **SW_01_2_H_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F110.ACT.FORCE	Force recorded by the actuator in DaN (Deca Newtons)
3	ACT.DISPLLASER.GTX80	Displacement recorded by the load actuator in mm
4	P147	Pore pressures at the top of the anchor in kPa
5	P172	Pore pressures at the bottom of the anchor in kPa
6	P170	Pore pressures at one diameter depth below the anchor in kPa

File **SW_01_3_H_MO**:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F110.ACT.FORCE	Force recorded by the actuator in DaN (Deca Newtons)
3	ACT.DISPLLASER.GTX80	Displacement recorded by the load actuator in mm
4	P148	Pore pressures at the top of the anchor in kPa
5	P173	Pore pressures at the bottom of the anchor in kPa
6	P178	Pore pressures at one diameter depth below the anchor in kPa

The T-bar tests contain three columns organised as follows:

Column	Id	Description
1	time	Measurement time in seconds
2	F.Tbar	Force recorded by the T-bar load cell in DaN
3	z.Tbar	Displacement recorded by the T-bar actuator in mm

7.4 Other files

From the centrifuge experiments there were retrieved video sequences during the loading tests. The records are from two cameras, then the files are identified as follows:

SW_C_CC_CCC.mp4

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
C	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
CC	Anchor identifier: A01, A02,A03
CCC	Camera employed: CAM1, CAM2

For example, data set SW_01 A01 _CAM1 corresponds to centrifuge test 01, anchor 1 (A01), recorded by camera 1 (CAM1).

Several water content samples were obtained before and after the centrifuge test (Figure 11), the data file **SW_01_water_content.csv** contains the water content values obtained after the centrifuge test at two locations, identified as Column 1 and Column 2. In addition, the average value of the water content of the clay before consolidation is included (initial).

Figure 11: Water content profiles

The geometry of the experimental setup of the loading tests is provided in .DXF files that can be opened in any Computed Asisted Design (CAD) application. The files are identified as follows:

SW_D_DD_SETUP.dxf

Where,

SW	Abbreviation of the project name ShareWind
D	Test number: 01, 02, 03 ...
DD	Anchor identifier: A01, A02,A03

8 References

- Madabhushi, S.P.G., 2014, Centrifuge modelling for civil engineers, CRC Press, Boca Raton.
- Stewart, D.P., and Randolph, M.F. 1991. A new site investigation tool for the centrifuge. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Centrifuge Modelling, Centrifuge '91, Boulder, Colo., 13–14 June 1991. Balkema, Rotterdam, the Netherlands. pp. 531–538.